

Electrical Conductance of Cobalt(III) Complexes of Acetylpyridinethiosemicarbazone Halides in Methanol at 25°

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Manuscript received 25 April 1991, revised 28 October 1991,
accepted 31 December 1991

THE Fuoss-Onsager equation for 1:1 electrolytes¹ has been applied to study the electrolytic conductance of the Co^{III} complexes of acetylpyridinethiosemicarbazone halides in methanol at 25°. The effect of the solvated anion size on the conductance of these complexes has been discussed in the light of the variation of both the association constant K_A and the closest distance of approach a (Å). The solvent-separated ion-pair model has been applied in an attempt to analyse the values of K_A obtained.

Experimental

Cobalt(III) complexes of acetylpyridinethiosemicarbazone halides² were recrystallised from ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over P₂O₅. The preparation of pure methanol, methods of preparation of solutions and measurements of conductance were the same as reported earlier³.

Results and Discussion

The conductance data (Table 1) were treated by the Fuoss-Shedlovsky equation. Using Λ_0 from this treatment, the data were fitted to the Fuoss-Onsager equation³. The value of a was calculated in the same manner³. The characteristic parameters derived from the above treatment is presented in Table 2.

TABLE 1—CONDUCTANCE OF Co^{III} COMPLEXES OF ACETYLPIRIDINETHIOSEMICARBAZONE HALIDES IN METHANOL AT 25°

Cl ⁻ complex		Br ⁻ complex		I ⁻ complex	
10 C	Λ	10°C	Λ	10°C	Λ
25 220	74.211	17.678	83 660	14.400	89.988
23.262	75.003	16.461	84.086	13.521	90.423
21.700	75 615	15.510	84.491	12 655	90 824
20.195	76 228	14.878	84.745	11 882	91 229
18 815	76 870	13 813	85.203	11.126	91.611
17.226	77.592	12 729	85.745	10.194	92.534
16 030	78.145	11 852	86.113	9.488	92 958
14.852	78.725	11.104	86.494	8.793	92.319
13.748	79.254	10.349	86 865	8 219	93.319
12.755	79 811	9 510	87 318	7 676	93.655
11 946	80.256	8.826	87.702	7.191	93 978
10.975	80 782	8 236	88.000	6.729	94 283
10 017	81 382	7 720	88.349	6 330	94 576
		7.219	88 640	5.898	94 880
		6 740	88 907	5.485	95.171
		6 231	89 222	5 078	95 495
		5.740	89 562	4 780	95.719
		5.237	89.927		

distance of approach between the cation and the anion increases in the same order, it is expected that the force of attraction would increase in the order, I⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻. In our case, an opposite trend for the variation of K_A was obtained.

Pethybridge and Spiers⁵ obtained a similar trend for solvation in the case of *trans*-dinitrobis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) salts of Cl⁻, Br⁻ and I⁻ in water at 25°. They found that the order of solvation was Cl⁻ > Br⁻ > I⁻. El-Hammamy *et al.*^{6,7}, measured the conductance of Co^{II} complexes of acetone-thiosemicarbazone and acetophenone-thiosemicarbazone halides in methanol at 25° and found that Λ_0 increased for the Co^{II} complexes from Cl⁻ to I⁻ according to the ionic equivalent conductance of anions. The values of a and K_A decreased with the increase of size of the solvated anion, which is in agreement with our results. The decreasing values of K_A with increasing size of the solvated anion in the present case can be explained in the light of the

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISTIC PARAMETERS FOR Co^{III} COMPLEXES OF ACETYLPIRIDINETHIOSEMICARBAZONE HALIDES IN METHANOL AT 25° DERIVED FROM FUOSS-ONSAGER EQUATION

Salt	Λ_0	J	a (Å)	K_A	σ_A
[Co(APT) ₂] ₂ Cl	92 651 ± 0.886	1 923.1	5.947 ± 0.062	73.918 ± 2.135	0.041 8
[Co(APT) ₂] ₂ Br	96.774 ± 0.488	1 880.7	5.504 ± 0.072	40.629 ± 10.167	0.233 7
[Co(APT) ₂] ₂ I	102.600 ± 0.408	1 846 8	5.011 ± 0.084	43.226 ± 11.554	0.011 6

It is seen from Table 2 that Λ_0 increases from the Cl⁻ complex to the I⁻ complex according to the increase of the ionic equivalent conductance of the anions. The values of J and a decrease with increasing size of the solvated anions. This supports the view that for salts with a common cation, the size of the solvated anion becomes the essential factor in controlling the extent of ion-pairing⁴. The solvation of these anions of Co^{III}-acetylpyridinethiosemicarbazone halides increases in the order, Cl⁻ > Br⁻ > I⁻, which is in accordance with the trend of a . From the electrostatic point of view, since the closest

U term. The values of the U term for the Co^{III} complexes of acetylpyridinethiosemicarbazone halides are calculated³ and given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—CALCULATED VALUES OF K_1 AND U FOR Co^{III} COMPLEXES OF ACETYLPIRIDINETHIOSEMICARBAZONE HALIDES IN METHANOL AT 25°

Salt	K_A	K_1	K_2	U
[Co(APT) ₂] ₂ Cl	73.918	9.508	6.775	2.051
[Co(APT) ₂] ₂ Br	40.629	9.508	3.273	1.453
[Co(APT) ₂] ₂ I	43.226	9.750	3.433	1.489

TABLE 4—CALCULATION OF RADII OF IONS FOR Co^{II} COMPLEXES OF ACETYL-PYRIDINETHIOSEMICARBAZONE HALIDES IN METHANOL, AT 25°

Salt	Λ_0	$\lambda_0^- \eta_0$	λ_0^-	λ_0^+	Av. λ_0^+	R^+	R^-	$R^+ + R^-$	$a(\text{Å})$
[Co(APT) ₂]Cl	92.651	0.2850	52.31	40.31	40.385	3.728	2.875	6.603	5.947
[Co(APT) ₂]Br	96.774	0.3065	56.26	40.51	±0.114	3.713	2.673	6.386	5.504
[Co(APT) ₂]I	102.600	0.3394	62.30	40.30		3.731	2.414	6.146	5.011

It can be seen that the U term decreases slowly as the anionic size increases, i.e. the ion-dipole interaction term (E_z/KT) predominates over the entropy term. The calculated values of K_1 and K_2 are given in Table 3. It can be seen that K_2 decreases as the anionic size increases, the ion-pair prefers the more solvated form, and the disturbance due to the orientation of solvent molecules around the ion decreases by increasing the anionic size.

Radii of ions: The electrostatic radii R^+ and R^- are given by equation,

$$R^+ = 0.8194 \times 10^{-8} / \lambda_0^+ \eta_0$$

In the present case λ_0^- values were obtained from the intercepts of the straight-line plots of the Walden product $\Lambda_0 \eta_0$ vs reciprocal of the molecular weight as previously discussed³. To calculate λ_0^+ for (Co^{III} complexes)⁴, the average value obtained for λ_0^+ in case of Cl⁻, Br⁻ and I⁻ complexes was used in the calculations. Applying Stoke's equation, one may obtain both R^+ and R^- . The data are recorded in Table 4, where the value of a is found to be less than the summation of the electrostatic radii of the cation and the anion; this behaviour can be probably attributed to ion association⁸.

From conductance data Hughes and Hartley⁹, using the Stoke's equation, had found that ions possess smaller size in water than in alcohols or acetone.

El-Hammamy *et al.* studied the conductance behaviour in case of acetylcholine halides and perchlorate in water¹⁰, methanol³, ethanol¹¹ and n-propanol¹² at 25°, and found that whereas in water the values of a are greater than the summation of electrostatic radii, the reverse is true in the case of the different alcohols. Surprisingly, low values of a from Stoke's radii for different salts in different alcohols are probably due to ion association⁸. The electrostatic radius of anion R^- is found to decrease with increasing anionic size.

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